

READING STRATEGIES OF KWL METHOD IN READING CONTENT

Qobulova Maxfuza, Ismailova Nozimaxon

Students of Tashkent region Chirchik state pedagogical institute

ABSTRACT

This article is dedicated to study of the use of KWL method and strategy in given texts.

Key words: teaching, reading, methods, process, know, learning, research.

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays there are some difficulties in reading texts and analyze the text among students. Many methods are beneficial as well as KWL method which enhance students reading skill. KWL, an acronym for **K**now, Want-to-know, and Learned, is an effective way to read with purpose. KWL is easy to apply and can lead to significant improvement in your ability to learn efficiently and to retain what you have learned.

METHODOLOGY

The first thing to mention is that the active steps follow the acronym KWL and are generally organized in the form of a three-column chart:

KNOW	WANT-TO-KNOW	LEARNED
Before reading, assess and record what you know.	Set a purpose for your reading. What do you want to learn from the text? As you read, maintain focus on your purpose.	After reading, reflect, note and review what you learned from your reading.

In column 1, write down what you know about the text's topic. What have you read, heard, or experienced that is related to the topic? What is the context? Who is the author? When was the text written? Who published it?

In column 2, continue your pre-reading work, noting what you want to know after reading the text. What do you want to know? What you write in this column could refer to your personal goals; in academic reading, however, it will more likely have to do with what you need to learn from the reading for your class. What does this text have to do with the learning outcomes for your class? How does it relate to other reading assignments or material you are covering in class? How does it reinforce or challenge what you are learning, exploring or discussing in class?

Preview the text, observing title, prefatory material, headings and subheadings, and any charts, pictures, or other visuals. Compile a list of questions based on what you've determined you want to know to focus your reading.

In column 3, answer and record the answers to questions you posed before you began reading. Write down the main ideas from the text, as well as what you found surprising, controversial or hard to understand. Compare what you've written in the "learned column to what you wrote in the "want-to-know" column. Have you accomplished what you set out to accomplish in your reading? Consider ways in which what you learned helps you understand ideas or concepts being explored in your class.

What is a KWL chart?

A KWL chart is an organizational tool primarily used by students and teachers to direct and facilitate learning in the classroom.

K-W-L is an acronym that stands for "Know," "Want to Know," and "Learned." The KWL chart is divided into three columns—one for each letter—under which students record:

1. What they already know about the topic
2. What they want to know (or questions they have) about the topic
3. What they learned (after the lesson or assignment)

KWL charts are effective tools for engaging students in the learning process, helping them recall knowledge, and tracking their learning progress. While they are

often used to help students improve their reading comprehension, KWL charts can be applied to any topic or lesson.

The KWL reading strategy is an instructional technique used to improve reading comprehension. It also improves a student's ability to remember the material. KWL is most often used with expository reading materials such as classroom textbooks, research articles, and journalistic pieces.

How to use a KWL chart

To use a KWL chart, first create a table with three columns—one for each letter: K-W-L. You can draft the worksheet by hand or use an online KWL chart.

Lucid chart can help you get started with a premade, printable KWL chart template. Click the image below to start your own KWL chart.

Once you have your chart, follow these steps to fill it out before, during, and after the lesson:

Start with column 1: Know

Under the first column, have students share what they already know about (or associate with) the topic at hand.

You can use the KWL chart for both group and individual learning. You may want to break the class up into small groups and then have each team share their notes with the rest of the class.

Consider drawing a chart on the board (or pulling up an online KWL chart on the projector) to fill out together as a class. Students can also fill out their own worksheets individually as you go to help them stay on track through the lesson.

This is a great way for teachers to see what the class already understands collectively and plan their lessons accordingly. For instance, Column 1 can help teachers to identify any misconceptions students may have going into a lesson.

Depending on the situation, you may want to correct students at this stage or simply use the information to plan your lesson to ensure those misconceptions are clarified later in the curriculum.

Pro tip: Come prepared with additional questions to prompt the students to brainstorm and guide their thought process.

Fill out column 2: Want to know

Once you've identified what you (or your class) already know, the next step is to fill out the "W" column. Have students answer: What do you want to know about this topic?

Again, you may want to split the class into smaller groups or pairs to start the discussion and then have them share their ideas with the whole class to record on a master KWL sheet. If your class doesn't have much experience with or knowledge of the topic, provide prompting questions to help them brainstorm.

Adding "Who, What, When, Where, Why, How" to the top of the column is often enough to spark ideas and get the conversation flowing.

This step is a powerful teaching aid because it helps teachers identify student interests and questions on a topic and adapt their lesson plans accordingly. When done well, the result is more engaged students and more effective learning outcomes.

Complete column 3: Learned

Throughout the lesson or unit, students can refer to their KWL chart and fill out the third column: Learned.

Here they will record what they are learning and check off the questions they had listed in the second column that were answered. Students can share anything they found interesting or surprising and identify any misconceptions they might have had from Column 1.

CONCLUSION

To sum up, knowing this method develop students reading skill easier and save their essential time. Some teachers like to have students fill out their KWL charts throughout the unit as they go, while others wait until the end of the unit to have students record everything they learned. Either way, this stage provides students the opportunity to review their learning and helps teachers track student progress and learning outcomes. Though it was introduced as a strategy for reading comprehension, the KWL method can be applied to any learning situation, such as

taking a class, listening to a lecture, watching a documentary, participating in a classroom activity, attending a workshop and so on.

THE LIST OF USED LITERATURE

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